

Welcome to the WPO Applicant Customer Experience & Satisfaction Survey!

The purpose of this survey is to gather applicant feedback about the Weather Program Office's (WPO) proposal submission and application process associated with funding competitions. Each year, WPO hosts funding competitions encouraging the submission of research proposals that aim to conduct and transition weather research. WPO staff continually strive to streamline the proposal submission process for its funding competitions. However, without feedback on how applicants currently interpret, understand, and view WPO's funding competitions, it is difficult to make informed decisions on how to refine the submission and application process for future competitions. Therefore, this survey will be conducted on a yearly basis to obtain critical stakeholder feedback with the hope of continuing to improve WPO's proposal submission and application process.

Public Burden Statement

A Federal agency may not conduct or sponsor, and a person is not required to respond to, nor shall a person be subject to a penalty for failure to comply with an information collection subject to the requirements of the Paperwork Reduction Act of 1995 unless the information collection has a currently valid OMB Control Number. The approved OMB Control Number for this information collection is 0690-0030. Without this approval, we could not conduct this survey. Public reporting for this information collection is estimated to be approximately 10-20 minutes per response, including the time for reviewing instructions, searching existing data sources, gathering and maintaining the data needed, and completing and reviewing the information collection. All responses to this information collection are voluntary. Send comments regarding this burden estimate or any other aspect of this information collection, including suggestions for reducing this burden to the WPO, Castle Williamsberg, Castle.Williamsberg@noaa.gov.

Basic Information and Grant History

Please provide a little information about yourself and your grant history.

1. Which of the following best describes your project role on the proposal(s) you submitted to the WPO Notice of Funding Opportunity this year?
 - Lead Principal Investigator
 - Co-Principal Investigator
 - Co-Investigator
 - I submitted multiple proposals, so I am both a Lead PI and a Co-PI on a proposal.
 - Other (please specify)

2. Which of the following describes your current organizational affiliation? Please select all that apply. (1 point)
 - Large research university (i.e., Doctoral, Masters, and Professional Colleges & Universities)
 - Primarily undergraduate institution
 - Minority serving institution (i.e., a Tribal College or University, an Historically Black College or University, or an Hispanic-Serving Institution.)
 - Community college
 - Technical institute
 - NOAA Cooperative Institute
 - NOAA Cooperative Science Center
 - Non-profit organization (NPO)
 - Non-governmental organization (NGO)
 - Private sector organization or company
 - Community-based organization (CBO)
 - Other (please specify)

3. Not including any proposals submitted for this funding competition, how many proposals **have you submitted to NOAA** (including WPO and other NOAA offices) **in the past?** [If > 0 continue to Q3, otherwise continue to Q6] (1 point)

4. [If Q3 > 0] Not including any proposals submitted for this funding competition, how many of your proposals **submitted to NOAA** (including WPO and other NOAA offices) **have been awarded in the past?** (1 point)

5. [If Q3 > 0] Not including the proposals submitted for this funding competition, how many proposals have you submitted **specifically to the Weather Program Office** (previously known as the Office of Weather and Air Quality) **in the past?** (1 point)

6. [If Q3 > 0] Not including the proposals submitted for this funding competition, how many of your proposals **submitted to the Weather Program Office** (previously known as the Office of Weather and Air Quality) **have been awarded in the past?** (1 point)

Basic Information about This Year's NOFO Competition (FY25)

Now, please provide some basic information **about your experience applying to this year's Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO).**

7. Which Weather Program Office competition(s) did you apply to **this year?** Please select all that apply. (1 point)
- Observations (Obs)
 - Social, Behavioral, and Economic Sciences (SBES)
 - Testbeds
 - Air Quality Research and Forecasting (AQRF)
 - VORTEX-USA
 - Subseasonal to Seasonal (S2S)
8. How did you hear about **this year's** WPO Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO)? Please select all that apply. (1 point)
- Grants.gov
 - WPO Website
 - WPO NOFO Webinar
 - National Weather Service (NWS) Email List
 - NOAA Science Seminar Series Email List
 - NOAA Central Library Series Email List
 - WPO Email List
 - X (formerly known as Twitter)
 - LinkedIn
 - Facebook
 - Informed by a Colleague
 - Other (please specify)

Resources for Completing Your Application Package

Please complete the following questions that ask about resources the Weather Program Office (WPO) provides to assist principal investigators when completing their Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO) application materials.

WPO Website

9. Did you visit the Weather Program Office's website prior to preparing your Letter of Intent (LOI) and/or proposal application materials?
- Yes
 - No
 - I'm not sure
10. [If Yes to Q9] Please think about your experience using WPO's website. Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly agree*. [[U.S. Department of Education 2020 Grantee Satisfaction Survey](#)] (3 points)
- It was easy to find specific information about the Notices of Funding Opportunities (NOFO) on the WPO website.
 - The content and materials on the WPO website were helpful while putting together my NOFO application materials.
 - I was able to accomplish what I wanted to when I visited the WPO website.

WPO Webinar

11. Did you watch the WPO FY25 Funding Opportunity (NOFO) webinar prior to preparing your LOI and/or proposal application materials?
- Yes—I watched the webinar live.
 - Yes—I watched the recorded webinar on my own time.
 - No—I did NOT watch the webinar.
 - I did not know a webinar about the FY25 NOFO existed.
12. [If Yes to Q11] Thinking about your experience watching this year's NOFO webinar, please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly disagree*. (3 points)
- I found the webinar helpful when preparing my application materials.
 - I gained new knowledge about WPO's funding opportunities from the webinar.
 - The webinar addressed questions I had about WPO's funding opportunities.

Other Resources

13. Thinking about your experience preparing your application materials, how **useful** were the following resources to you? Please rate the usefulness of each resource on a scale from 1 = not at all useful to 5 = very useful. If you did not use a particular resource or did not know this resource existed, please select one of those options instead (1 point)
- NOFO General Information Sheet
 - Specific Competition Information Sheet (e.g., Testbeds Info Sheet)
 - Applicant Checklist (on WPO website)

- Title Page Templates (on WPO website)
- Abstract Template (on WPO website)
- NOFO Frequently Asked Questions (on WPO website)

14. What, if anything, could WPO do to improve these resources for future funding competitions? What other resources could WPO provide to improve the NOFO application process in the future? If you have feedback about a specific resource, please remember to include its name in your response. (6 points)

Interactions with WPO Program Staff

15. Did you interact with Weather Program Office (WPO) program staff prior to submitting your Letter of Intent (LOI) or proposal application materials?

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

16. [If Yes to Q15] Think about the interactions you had with WPO staff. Please indicate your level of agreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree. (3 points)

- I found my interactions with WPO staff helpful when preparing my application materials.
- I gained new knowledge about WPO's funding opportunity from my interactions with WPO staff.
- My interactions with WPO staff addressed questions I had about WPO's funding opportunity.
- I felt comfortable reaching out to WPO staff with questions about WPO's funding opportunity.
- I know that I can ask questions about WPO's funding opportunity by sending an email to the WPO competition email address.

17. [If No or I'm not sure to Q15] You indicated that you **did not** interact with WPO program staff. Please indicate your level of agreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree to help us better understand why you did not reach out.

- I did not know that I could reach out to Weather Program Office (WPO) program staff with questions.
- I had trouble locating contact information for WPO program staff and/or competition managers.
- Now that I know I can reach out to WPO program staff and/or competition managers, I am likely to do this in the future.

Reading and Interpreting the NOFO Document

The next few questions will ask you about finding, reading, and understanding the information in the Weather Program Office (WPO) Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO) announcement.

18. Thinking about your experience with the NOFO announcement(s), please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where *1 = strongly disagree* and *5 = strongly agree*. (8 points)
- It was easy to locate the NOFO announcement(s) on Grants.gov.
 - The NOFO announcement(s) was clear and easy to understand.
 - The eligibility criteria included in the NOFO announcement(s) were clear and easy to understand.
 - It was easy to determine whether my project was a good fit given the priorities outlined in the NOFO announcement(s).
 - The NOFO announcement(s) took a reasonable amount of time to read.
 - It was easy to determine whether my project needed a NOAA Request for Federal Support.
 - The review criteria included in the NOFO announcement were appropriate to judge the best science and move the field forward.
 - The science priorities included in the NOFO announcement addressed important scientific research gaps..
19. When you were preparing your application, did you have trouble finding any important information in the Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO) announcement? If so, please select the different types of information that you found **challenging to locate and/or understand in the announcement**. Select all that apply. (8 points)
- Competition Research Priorities
 - Evaluation Criteria
 - Review and Selection Process
 - Eligibility Information
 - What to Include in a Letter of Intent
 - How to Submit a Letter of Intent
 - What to Include in a Full Proposal
 - How to Submit a Full Proposal
 - Budget Information and Forms
 - Information for Federal Collaborators (i.e., NOAA Request for Federal Collaborators)
 - Testbed Collaboration Form
 - Deadline(s) for Submission
 - Project Start and End Date
 - Dollar Limit on Awards
 - Page Limitation Instructions
 - Formatting Instructions
 - Information about Readiness Levels

- Federal Program Manager Contact Information
- Other (Please Specify):

20. [open-ended] What, if anything, can WPO do to make it easier to find and understand important information in the NOFO announcement? (6 points)

LOI Submission

21. Did you submit a Letter of Intent (LOI) prior to submitting your full proposal application? (1 point)

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

22. [If No to Q30] What was the reason for not submitting a LOI prior to submitting your full proposal application? (2 points)

- I did not know what a LOI was.
- I was not aware that I could submit a LOI before submitting my full proposal.
- I did not have enough time to submit a LOI.
- I did not know about this funding opportunity until after the LOI due date.
- It was not required, so I intentionally chose not to submit a LOI even though I had enough time.
- Other? [Please specify]

23. [If Yes to Q30] Please estimate the amount of time (rounded to the nearest hour) that you spent preparing your Letter of Intent (LOI). (1 point)

24. [If Yes to Q30] WPO uses both a Smartsheet form and email submission to collect Letters of Intent. Thinking about your experience using the Smartsheet form to submit your Letter of Intent, please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly agree*. If you did not submit via Smartsheet Form, please choose that option. (3 points)

- It was easy to use the Smartsheet form to submit my Letter of Intent.
- The Smartsheet form was clear and easy to understand.
- I would prefer submitting my Letter of Intent via email in the future.

25. [If Yes to Q30] Did you receive feedback from the Weather Program Office about your Letter of Intent?

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure
- I submitted an LOI to more than one competition and only received feedback for one of my LOIs.

26. [If Yes to Q30] Thinking about the feedback you received from WPO about your Letter of Intent, please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly agree*. (3 points)

- I received constructive feedback that helped improve my proposal.
- The feedback I received was clear and easy to understand.
- I received feedback in a timely manner.

27. The Weather Program Office wants to better understand the optimal amount of time that applicants need to prepare a Letter of Intent. Therefore, in your opinion, how many weeks are needed to **sufficiently prepare a Letter of Intent?** (1 point)

- Less than one week
- 1 week
- 2 weeks
- 3 weeks
- 4 weeks
- 5 weeks
- 6 weeks
- More than 6 weeks

28. The Weather Program Office wants to better understand the optimal amount of time that applicants need to prepare their full proposal using Letter of Intent feedback. Therefore, in your opinion, how many weeks are needed to **sufficiently prepare your full proposal using Letter of Intent feedback?** (1 point)

- One week or less
- 2 weeks
- 3 weeks
- 4 weeks
- 5 weeks
- 6 weeks
- More than 6 weeks

Proposal Submission

29. Please estimate the amount of time (rounded to the nearest hour) that you spent to prepare your proposal and other application materials (excluding the LOI), and submit your proposal in Grants.gov. (1 point)

30. Did you have institutional support (e.g., Grants Administrator) that helped you prepare application materials and/or submitted your proposal? (1 point)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

31. Thinking about your experience completing your proposal and other application materials, please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly agree*. (5 points)

- The amount of work and time needed to complete my proposal was appropriate for the level of available funding.
- I feel confident that I provided the appropriate Readiness Levels for my project proposal and proposed project outputs.
- It was easy to complete the budget forms (SF-424) for my application package. *[Skip if Answered Yes to Q25]*
- The amount of work and time invested in crafting my data management plan was appropriate to ensure compliance with the latest data management requirements.
- I had all of the information I needed to complete my proposal.
- I felt comfortable collecting information from my collaborators for the voluntary Underserved Groups Information Request. [N/A option]
- It was clear to me that providing information for the Underserved Groups Information Request was voluntary.

32. After you submitted your application on grants.gov, it routed through the eRA system. Thinking about your experience with the eRA system, please indicate your agreement or disagreement with each of the following statements, where 1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly agree*.

- It was clear that the lead PI on my proposal needed an eRA account to submit the final proposal.
- I clearly understood the submission requirements for the eRA system before submitting my final proposal.
- The eRA proposal formatting requirements were easy to understand.
- The time it took for my proposal to pass through both the grants.gov and eRA validation checks was reasonable.
- The process for addressing any eRA validation errors was clear and easy to follow.
- I clearly understood that eRA validation errors needed to be addressed, while validation warnings did not require action for my proposal to be considered “successfully submitted.”

Changes to the NOFO Process

The next few questions will ask you about specific changes that were made to the Weather Program Office (WPO) Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO) process and announcement(s).

Change from a Single Announcement to Multiple Individual Announcements

33. As a result of NOAA's grant management system change, WPO launched six (6) individual Notices of Funding Opportunities in FY25, each representing a single competition (e.g., Social, Behavioral, and Economic Sciences NOFO, Observations NOFO), instead of a single omnibus Notice of Funding Opportunity.

Please reflect on your experience with the transition to six (6) individual Notice of Funding Opportunity announcements (NOFO) in FY25. Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree:

- The individual NOFO announcements made it difficult to find research priorities relevant to my work.
- Reviewing several individual NOFO announcements increased my workload and created additional burden.
- The individual NOFO announcements increased my interest in applying to multiple competitions.
- I would prefer this approach of using individual NOFO announcements for future WPO funding opportunities.

Changes to the Collaboration Form

34. Based on applicant feedback, WPO renamed the Collaboration Form to the Testbed Collaboration Form and clarified its submission requirements in the FY25 Notice of Funding Opportunity.

Please reflect on your experience with the Testbed Collaboration Form process in the FY25 Notice of Funding Opportunity and indicate your level of agreement with the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree:

- It was easy to determine whether my project required a Testbed Collaboration Form.
- The instructions for when to submit the Testbed Collaboration Form were clear.
- The clarification about when to use the Testbed Collaboration Form helped me save time when preparing my application.
- I would prefer the Testbed Collaboration Form continue to be used in this way in future WPO funding opportunities.

Changes to Letters of Support

35. Based on applicant feedback, WPO renamed the Letters of Support to a Request for NOAA Federal Support and clarified its submission requirements in the FY25 Notices of Funding Opportunities.

Please consider your experience with the Request for NOAA Federal Support (previously known as “Letters of Support”) in the FY25 Notice of Funding Opportunity and indicate your level of agreement with the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree:

- I have a clear understanding of when and why the Request for NOAA Federal Support would be required.
- It was clear that I needed to submit a Request for NOAA Federal Support only if my project’s budget intended to include eligible funding requests by NOAA federal collaborators.
- The clarification on when the Request for NOAA Federal Support is needed saved me time when preparing my application.
- I would prefer the Request for NOAA Federal Support to continue being used in this way in future WPO funding opportunities.

Changes to Abstract Reporting Requirements

36. WPO changed the abstract reporting requirements from a paragraph to short sentence prompts in the FY25 Notice of Funding Opportunities.

Please reflect on your experience writing the abstract for your final proposal submission for the FY25 Notices of Funding Opportunities. Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree:

- I found the abstract template helpful when writing my abstract.
- The short sentence prompts reduced the time and effort needed to write my abstract.
- There was information I wanted to include with my abstract that did not fit within the provided short sentence prompts.
- I would prefer to continue using this short sentence prompt format in future WPO funding opportunities.

Increased Time Applicants Have Between Receiving LOI Feedback and Final Proposal Due Date

37. Based on previous applicant feedback, WPO extended the period of time applicants have between receiving Letter of Intent feedback and submitting final proposal materials to 6 weeks in the FY25 Notice of Funding Opportunity.

Please reflect on your experience with the timeline between receiving Letter of Intent (LOI) feedback and submitting your final proposal in the FY25 Notices of Funding Opportunities. Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements, where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree:

- The additional time between receiving LOI feedback and the final proposal deadline was helpful for incorporating LOI feedback into my proposal materials.
- The additional time improved the quality of my application materials.
- The extended timeframe allowed sufficient time to coordinate with my project team and collaborators.
- The additional time gave me sufficient time to coordinate with my institutional support staff (e.g., Grants Administrator).
- The extended timeframe reduced stress during proposal preparation.
- I would like to see this extended timeframe continued in future WPO funding opportunities.

38. What was one change in the FY25 Notices of Funding Opportunities that you found particularly helpful or challenging, and why?

Final Questions

Please complete these final questions that ask about your overall experience applying to the Weather Program Office's (WPO) Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO).

39. Overall, how satisfied are you with WPO's Notice of Funding Opportunity application process? (1 point)

- Very dissatisfied,
- dissatisfied,
- neither satisfied nor dissatisfied,
- satisfied,
- very satisfied

40. Compared to other funding agencies, WPO's Notice of Funding Opportunity application process is... (1 point)

- Much easier to complete,
- somewhat easier to complete,
- about the same level of difficulty to complete,

- somewhat harder to complete, and
- much harder to complete.
- I have never submitted to another funding agency, so I cannot answer this question

41. [open-ended] What is the single most important thing that WPO could do to improve its grant application process and your experience submitting a proposal to future competitions?

42. [open-ended] Is there anything else you want to share with us about your experience applying to WPO's Notice of Funding Opportunity this year?